

Spin Classifications – The Coupling Constants Series – 8 Theory

O Manor

June 18, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing the coupling constants primorial series derived in March 2021, in its first and second representations, it is possible to classify according to spin representation the interactions which propagated to a long range, and the interactions propagating toward a short range such as the graviton and the color charge. That is the same representation we used for explaining particle wave duality in the 8-theory thesis.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1.16)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.17)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.18)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.19)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N + 1$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N + 1$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N + 1$$

If the overall term in the coupling is summed up to become odd, i.e. $2N + 1$, the bosons propagated is long ranged and stable, such as the photon for the third coupling term. Such coupling terms have only one element of N_V outside of the parenthesis. We have seen that there is no limitation regarding the net variation and there could be higher spin coupling terms such as gravity. Which has spin two. The important point one wanted to emphasize in short essay is that odd amount in the coupling term is synonymous with long range propagation, and even amount with short ranged propagation, such as the strong and gravity. Spin two is synonymous with even number of variations which vanish as we covered in previous papers regarding gravity.

$$[2N(g) + 2] \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} = [(2N(g)) + (3)] + N_{V1} + N_{V2} + N_{V3} \quad (1.191)$$

Another important point to emphasize is that is no limit regarding the spin or amount of net variations clustering which could be made. There could higher terms than spin two such as gravity. The additional terms added was the key idea to the particle wave duality presented in the 8-theory thesis. Measuring a photon is synonymous with adding an half unit spin to it, correlating to fermion spin and so varying his nature.

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.192)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma + \gamma \quad (1.193)$$

$$2N + 1 \rightarrow 2N + \frac{3}{2} \quad (1.194)$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)